

Synthesis and Structural Studies of the Complexes of Zn(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Co(II) with 3-Aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles

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Complexes of Zn(II), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) with 3-aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles have been prepared. They have been characterised on the basis of elemental analyses, infrared spectra, thermogravimetry, magnetic susceptibility and powder X-ray diffraction patterns. Fungitoxicity of the complexes and free ligands has been evaluated against *H. oryzae*. X-ray studies reveal that the complexes possess cubic structure.

COMPOUNDS containing triazole ring have been reported to have bactericidal^{1,2}, fungicidal^{3,4}, insecticidal^{5,6} and pesticidal^{7,8} properties. 3-Amino-1,2,4-triazole (Amizole) is a commercial herbicide. Importance of metal complexes has also been established and some of them are found to possess biological activity. Some drugs have increased activity when administered as metal complexes⁹ and a number of metal chelates inhibit tumour growth. The complexes of Co(II) and Cu(II) with 3-methyl-4-(2-pyridyl)-1,2,4-triazole-5-thiol have been reported¹⁰. The present communication reports the synthesis and characterisation of Zn(II), Co(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes with 3-aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of B. D. H. grade or of equivalent quality.

Preparation of 3-aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole: A mixture of an aryloxyacetylhydrazine (0.01 M) and arylisothiocyanate (0.012 M) was refluxed in NaOH solution (20 ml; 8%) for 5 to 6 hr when a clear solution resulted. It was cooled, poured into water and filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave a precipitate which was filtered, washed and recrystallised. The compounds, thus prepared, were characterised by elemental analyses and ir spectra (Table 1).

Preparation of metal complexes: The complexes were precipitated by refluxing a methanolic solution of 3-aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (0.01 M) with aqueous solution of a metal salt (0.03 M) for 4 to 6 hr. The precipitate was filtered, washed successively with large excess of water, hot methanol, ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Analyses of the metal complexes: Metal ions in the complexes were estimated by the methods in literature¹¹. The metal complexes were also analysed for their metal contents as their oxides.

For this purpose, weighed samples in silica crucible were first gently heated on a naked flame for 1 hr and then in an electric furnace at $800 \pm 10^\circ$ to a constant weight. These were cooled and weighed. Sulphur and nitrogen were estimated by the usual methods (Table 1).

TABLE 1—3-ARYLOXYMETHYL-4-ARYL-5-MERCAPTO-1,2,4-TRIAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	N% Found (Calcd.)	S% Found (Calcd.)
1.	2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ -	178	13.92 (14.14)	10.92 (10.77)
2.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ -	183	13.82 (13.20)	10.74 (10.06)
3.	*4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ -	150	12.94 (13.20)	10.83 (10.06)

IR Spectral Data $\nu_{\max}$ in cm ⁻¹					
*Conjugated	>C=N	p-disubstituted benzene	monosubstituted benzene	>C=S	>C-O-C<
1640		830	770	1175	1260

Physical measurements: The magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes were determined by Faraday method using ferrous ammonium sulphate as calibrant. Experimental magnetic susceptibilities were corrected for diamagnetism¹². The magnetic moments of the complexes at room temperature are given in Table 2.

The ir spectra of the complexes and the ligands were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, Model 621, in KBr phase in 4000-200 cm⁻¹ range.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex composition	Metal % Found (Calcd.)	N % Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M. Found (Calcd.)
[ZnL ₂ (Ac) ₂]	8.86 (8.36)	10.21 (10.81)	Diamagnetic
[ZnL ₂]Cl ₂	4.8 (4.90)	13.3 (12.68)	Diamagnetic
[CuL ₂ (Ac) ₂].H ₂ O	7.3 (7.60)	10.8 (10.45)	1.18 (1.73)
[Ni(NO ₃) ₂ L ₂ .2H ₂ O]	6.9 (6.86)	12.9 (13.10)	2.97 (2.83)
[Co(NO ₃) ₂ L ₂]	4.2 (4.05)	10.2 (10.34)	3.94 (3.87)

TABLE 3—CRYSTAL DATA FOR THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Lattice parameter and lattice type
[ZnL ₂ (Ac) ₂]	a = 20.6 Å Cubic
[CuL ₂ (Ac) ₂].H ₂ O	a = 17.70 Å Cubic
[Ni(NO ₃) ₂ L ₂ .2H ₂ O]	a = 18.69 Å Cubic
[Co(NO ₃) ₂ L ₂]	a = 21.38 Å Cubic

The thermogravimetry of the complexes were carried out with the help of a manual thermogravimetric analyser (supplied by P & D Division, FCI Ltd., Sindri) at a heating rate of 4° min⁻¹ in air. Results are recorded in Table 4.

TABLE 4—TG DATA FOR METAL COMPLEXES

Stable phase or thermal decomposition	Temp. range (°C)	% wt. loss Found (Calcd.)
ZnL ₂ (Ac) ₂	60-300	8.53 (7.59)
↓		
ZnL ₂ (Ac) ₂	300-540	46.85 (46.20)
↓		
ZnL(Ac)	540-700	88.83 (89.57)
↓		
ZnO		
ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	140-340	43.29 (44.86)
↓		
ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	340-700	90.90 (89.72)
↓		
ZnCl ₂		
CuL ₂ (Ac) ₂ .H ₂ O	80-160	1.90 (2.15)
↓		
CuL ₂ (Ac) ₂	160-460	47.908 (47.27)
↓		
CuL(Ac)	460-700	87.95 (90.48)
↓		
CuO		
Ni(NO ₃) ₂ .L ₂ .2H ₂ O	80-120	4.76 (4.21)
↓		
Ni(NO ₃) ₂ L ₂	120-360	42.77 (41.41)
↓		
Ni(NO ₃) ₂ L	360-660	93.56 (91.26)
↓		
NiO		
Co(NO ₃) ₂ L ₂	80-320	42.0 (43.71)
↓		
Co(NO ₃) ₂ L ₂	320-460	66.6 (65.56)
↓		
Co(NO ₃) ₂ L	460-700	96.0 (94.84)
↓		
CoO		

Powder X-ray diffraction patterns of the complexes were taken, using CuK radiation, employing a Guinier camera of 11.46 cm diam and X-ray unit of PW 1011 Philips, Holland. The diffraction patterns were indexed by Hessé-Lipson method. The agreement between the observed and calculated values of sin² θ_{hkl} was satisfactory which indicated that the indexing was correct.

Fungitoxicity of the complexes and the ligands were also evaluated against *H. oryzae* by agar-plate method¹³ at three different concentrations. The average per cent inhibition (Table 5) by various complexes were calculated by the expression :

$$\text{Per cent inhibition} = \frac{(C - T) \times 100}{C}$$

where C = diameter of the fungus colony in the control plate after 96 hr and T = diameter of the fungus colony in treated plates after 96 hr.

TABLE 5—FUNGICIDAL SCREENING (Organism—*H. oryzae*)

Average Percent Inhibition after 96 hr	Concentration		
	1 : 1,000	1 : 10,000	1 : 100,000
Zinc acetate complex	56.2	30.25	10.09
Zinc chloride complex	55.4	27.28	9.98
Ligand for the above complexes	44.9	21.30	11.05
Cobalt nitrate complex	45.2	22.75	12.54
Nickel nitrate complex	43.2	20.24	12.00
Ligand for the above complexes	33.9	19.25	9.25
Copper acetate complex	57.3	28.35	11.55
Ligand for the above complex	45.8	20.00	10.60

Results and Discussion

The zinc complexes are found diamagnetic as expected. The structure proposed for the complex is also in accordance with the diamagnetic behaviour. The magnetic moment value of Cu(II) acetate complex is found to be 1.18 B.M. This low value of magnetic moment could be explained by spin-spin interaction between two cupric ions, which is usually observed in other Cu(II) acetate complexes¹⁴. The magnetic moment value (2.97 B. M.) for Ni(II) complex lies well within the range accepted for the octahedral complexes of this metal ion¹⁵. The value of magnetic moment (3.94 B. M.) for Co(II) complexes is well within the range accepted for Co(II) complexes having three unpaired electrons.

The infrared spectra of ligands 3-tolyloxy-methyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole, 3-(*p*-chlorophenoxy)methyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole and 3-(*o*-chlorophenoxy)methyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole show bands at 3500, 3040 cm⁻¹; 3420, 3050 cm⁻¹ and 3412, 3025 cm⁻¹, respectively which may be assigned to ν_{asym}N-H and ν_{sym}N-H vibrations, respectively. A weak band in the region 2550-2600 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of these ligands may be assigned as ν_{S-H} stretching vibration. The bands observed at 1120, 1175 and 1060 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the respective ligands are

due to >C=S stretch. The ligand spectra show bands due to conjugated >C=N , *o*- and *p*-disubstituted benzene rings at 1735-1740, 960-1040 and 800-855 cm^{-1} , respectively. It may be concluded from these that the ligand exists in the following tautomeric form :

An analysis of the spectra of the complexes and their respective ligands shows that $\nu_{\text{S-H}}$ band in the region 2550-2600 cm^{-1} is absent in the spectra of the complexes whereas the $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ band is present. Further, there is a strong negative shift in $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ band in 1050-1200 cm^{-1} region. These clearly indicate that the thione form is favoured for complexation, coordination takes place through S atom of the thione and the ligands act as monodentate.

The asymmetric and symmetric >C=O stretching frequencies of free acetate ion observed at 1578 and 1425 cm^{-1} , respectively are observed at 1595 and 1430 cm^{-1} , respectively in Zn(II) acetate complex and at 1610 and 1440 cm^{-1} in Cu(II) acetate complex. A separation of about 165 and 160 cm^{-1} in the above modes in Zn(II) and Cu(II) acetate complexes suggests that the acetate group behaves as monodentate ligand in these complexes¹⁶. In Cu(II) acetate complex there is a band at 3560 cm^{-1} which is due to the presence of lattice water.

In case of Ni(II) and Co(II) nitrate complexes the presence of two bands at 1500, 1270 cm^{-1} and 1495, 1275 cm^{-1} , respectively due to ν_3 of nitrate group, indicates that the nitrate ion behaves as a monodentate ligand¹⁷.

Crystal data reported in Table 3 indicate that the crystal lattice of all the complexes belongs to cubic system. The lattice parameter of the complexes are also shown.

On the basis of thermoanalytical data, the mechanism of decomposition of complexes has been proposed and is shown in Table 4. The

decomposition products of all the complexes were analysed and the end products were found to be respective metal oxides except for zinc chloride complex. From the TG data it is clear that the mass loss starts at about 80°. The mass loss at a low rate right from the start may be due to desorption of adsorbed gases or moisture.

Fungicidal screening data (Table 5) indicate that the complexes are more fungitoxic than free ligand.

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References

1. S. C. BENNUR, V. B. JIGAJINNI and V. V. BADIGER, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1976, **21**, 757; *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, **84**, 94306j.
2. I. CHIYOMARA, E. YOSHINAGA and G. DOTIKE, *Jap. Pat.*, 1973, 460, 7339; *Chem. Abs.*, 1974, **81**, 73392m.
3. S. A. GREENFIELD, C. S. MICHAEL and W. C. VON MEYER, *Ger. Offen.*, 1974, 1, 806, 966; *Chem. Abs.*, **82**, 150485.
4. W. KRAEMER, K. H. BURCHEL, W. BRANDES and P. E. PROBERGER, *Ger. Offen.*, 1975, 352, 2,334; *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, **82**, 170967f.
5. G. TANAKA, *Japan Kokai*, 1974, 973, 7,495; *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, **82**, 156320h.
6. T. I. WAKINS and D. M. WRIGHTON, *Ger. Offen.*, 1976, 287, 2,530,287; *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, **84**, 135677f.
7. B. BOEHNER, W. MEYER and D. DOWES, SWISS, 1976, 206, 573; *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, **84**, 135677f.
8. L. GSELL and W. MEYER, *Ger. Offen.*, 1978, 084, 2,739; *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, **88**, 190844r.
9. D. R. WILLIAMS, *Chem. Rev.*, 1972, **203**, 72.
10. *Acta Pol. Pharm.*, 1976, **33**, 335.
11. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS, 1973.
12. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", (Eds) J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKINS, Interscience Publishers, Inc., N. Y., 1960, p. 400.
13. J. G. HORSFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1954, **11**, 357.
14. D. STAYA NARAYAN and B. K. MAHAPATRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 185.
15. F. A. COTTON and G. WILLKINSON, 3rd Edn., Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1972.
16. K. NAKAMOTO, J. FUJITA and S. TANAKA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 4904.
17. B. M. GARHOUSE, S. E. LIVINGSTON and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4222; *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, **8**, 75.